

WORKING PAPER

Once Set in Stone? Path Dependence in German Stem Cell Morality Policy:

From the Embryo Protection Act 1990 to the PID Law 2011

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Abstract

Building on Engeli and Rothmayr Allison's (2013) finding that Germany represents a distinctively restrictive outlier in European embryonic stem cell regulation, this working paper investigates whether the same path-dependent logic that shaped the Stem Cell Act 2002 (Stammzellgesetz) can also explain the configuration of the Preimplantation Genetic Diagnosis Act 2011 (PID-Gesetz). Drawing on a qualitative, deductive process-tracing analysis of Bundestag plenary protocols from 2002 and 2011, I test two hypotheses: first, that the 2011 PID debate reproduced the normative argumentative frames established in 2002 (H1); and second, that the same cross-party moral-policy coalitions that structured the 2002 debate re-emerged in 2011 (H2). Causal-process observations drawn from parliamentary debate transcripts provide substantial evidence for both hypotheses. The findings suggest that earlier normative decisions do not merely constitute historical context but operate as an active normative path that structures subsequent bioethical conflicts and limits the range of legitimate policy alternatives. The paper thereby confirms and extends the core results of Engeli and Rothmayr Allison for the most recent legislative episode in German bioethics.

Keywords: path dependence, morality policy, embryonic stem cell research, preimplantation genetic diagnosis, Germany, process tracing, Bundestag

1. Introduction

Few policy domains illustrate the long shadow of history more vividly than the regulation of embryonic research in Germany. While many Western European states have liberalised their legislative frameworks for stem cell research since the 1990s, Germany has consistently retained one of the most restrictive regulatory positions on the continent. Engeli and Rothmayr Allison (2013), in their comparative study of embryonic stem cell regulation across Western Europe, identify Germany as a particularly prominent 'special case' (Sonderfall); a country that has diverged from the permissive trend observed elsewhere, even under comparable scientific and economic pressures.

This working paper takes that finding as its starting point. Rather than revisiting the comparative dimension, I investigate the internal logic of Germany's regulatory trajectory by asking whether the mechanisms of path dependence, the idea that prior decisions systematically constrain and shape later ones, can explain the configuration of Germany's most recent piece of bioethics legislation: the Preimplantation Genetic Diagnosis Act of 2011 (PID-Gesetz). Specifically, I examine whether the Stem Cell Act of 2002 (Stammzellgesetz) established a normative path that structured the argumentation and coalition-building of the 2011 debate.

The question is theoretically significant. Path dependence in policy is well-established as an explanatory concept (Beyer, 2023; Banchoff, 2005), but empirical demonstration of its mechanisms, particularly in morality policy, where personal values and conscience votes are primary instead of monetary aspects, requires granular analysis of political processes rather

than cross-sectional comparison. I address this gap through a deductive, theory-testing process-tracing analysis (Starke, 2023) of Bundestag plenary protocols, using causal-process observations (CPOs) to trace a causal chain from the structure of the 2002 debate to the configuration of the 2011 debate.

The paper proceeds as follows. Section 2 reviews the theoretical framework of path dependence and its application to morality policy. Section 3 develops the research question and two hypotheses. Section 4 reviews the relevant literature on Germany as a bioethical special case and on moral-policy coalition formation. Section 5 outlines the methodological approach. Section 6 presents the empirical evidence. Section 7 concludes with a summary of findings and reflections on the limitations of the analysis.

2. Theoretical Framework: Path Dependence

The concept of path dependence, originating in economic history (David, 1985; Arthur, 1989) and later adopted in political science through historical institutionalism, rests on a fundamental premise: decisions made in the past shape, constrain, and often determine the decisions available in the present. As Beyer (2023, p. 127) summarises, institutions and policies accumulate a kind of inertia over time. The longer a rule persists and the more frequently it is applied, the greater its utility and the higher the costs of abandoning it. This dynamic of 'increasing returns' or 'positive feedback' is the core mechanism through which paths are created and sustained.

The implications of this logic for policy analysis are considerable. Policy outcomes shaped by path dependence exhibit four characteristic properties: they are to some degree **unpredictable** at the moment of origin (small initial differences can lead to large divergences over time); they are **inflexible** in the sense that the path becomes progressively harder to leave; they are **non-ergodic** (historical contingencies do not cancel each other out but accumulate); and they are potentially **inefficient** (the policy that 'wins' is not necessarily the optimal solution, but simply the one that became entrenched).

Path dependence is sustained through several interacting mechanisms. First, **increasing returns** ensure that the more an institutional arrangement is used, the more embedded it becomes; a dynamic also captured by the notion of lock-in. Second, **sequencing** matters: the order in which events and decisions occur shapes their content, because early decisions create templates that later decisions must either follow or consciously override. Third, **complementarity** between mutually dependent policies raises the cost of changing any one element of the system in isolation. Fourth, **power asymmetries** reinforce established arrangements, because incumbents who have adapted to existing rules have strong interests in their preservation. Fifth, **legitimacy** acts as a normative glue: what has been decided is perceived as right, and departures from it require justification.

A useful illustration from German social policy is the pension system. At its inception, Germany faced a genuine choice between a funded system (Kapitaldeckung) and a pay-as-you-go system (Umlageverfahren). Once the latter was introduced, switching costs became prohibitive, too many participants had organised their life plans around the existing system. Path dependence was complete (Marschallek, 2004). The analogy to bioethics is instructive: early normative settlements in legislation can generate similar lock-in effects, not through economic interdependence but through normative self-binding.

Path dependence does not mean that change is impossible. For a path to be abandoned, the mechanisms sustaining it must be reversed: increasing returns must give way to diminishing returns, power must shift, or established legitimacy must erode. In morality policy, such 'critical junctures' are rare precisely because value commitments are deeply held and resistant to the kind of instrumental recalculation that drives economic path-switching. This theoretical expectation informs our empirical analysis.

The concept has both explanatory strengths and acknowledged limitations. On the positive side, path dependence accounts for the persistence of policies even in the absence of ongoing functional justification, and explains why reform is often incremental rather than transformative. On the negative side, as critics have noted, the framework can underestimate the potential for change, and lacks a unified measurement standard. These limitations are acknowledged, but do not undermine the usefulness of the concept as an organising heuristic for the qualitative analysis that follows (Beyer, 2023).

3. Research Question and Hypotheses

The central research question of this paper is:

To what extent can the configuration of the Preimplantation Genetic Diagnosis Act 2011 be explained as a path-dependent continuation of prior policies, in particular the Stem Cell Act 2002?

This question unfolds along two dimensions, corresponding to two mechanisms of path dependence: the reproduction of normative frames (argumentative continuity) and the reproduction of political coalitions (structural continuity). I operationalise these dimensions in two hypotheses.

3.1 Hypothesis 1 (H1): Argumentative Continuity

The first hypothesis concerns the content of political arguments. Path dependence, understood as a mechanism of normative self-binding, predicts that prior normative settlements generate expectations of consistency. Deviations from established positions become politically and argumentatively costly — not merely because actors are strategically constrained, but because established normative frames carry accumulated legitimacy. If the 2002 debate established a specific vocabulary of bioethical argumentation — centred on concepts such as human dignity, the 'slippery slope', or research freedom, I would expect those same frames to structure the 2011 debate, and I would expect explicit backward references to the 2002 settlement to serve as instruments of normative self-binding.

H1: If the debate of 2002 was structured by normative guiding principles, then the PID debate of 2011 will reproduce the same argumentative patterns.

3.2 Hypothesis 2 (H2): Coalition Continuity

The second hypothesis concerns the structure of political alliances. Research on morality policy in Germany has shown that, on bioethical questions, party discipline is typically suspended in favour of individual conscience votes, and that the resulting coalition patterns do not follow the conventional left-right cleavage (Arzheimer, 2015; Engler & Dümig, 2017). Instead, two stable cross-party camps tend to form a restrictive coalition combining religious-conservative and ecologist-critical orientations, and a permissive coalition emphasising research freedom and individual self-determination. If these coalition patterns are indeed path-dependent, that is, if the 2002 alignment created normative commitments that constrained subsequent repositioning, I would expect the same cross-party groupings to re-emerge in 2011.

H2: If the stem cell debate of 2002 was structured by stable moral-policy coalitions, then the same coalition patterns will re-emerge in the PID debate of 2011.

It is important to clarify what these hypotheses are and are not about. I am not primarily interested in whether and how party indifference emerges in morality policy. That has been established elsewhere. Our concern is specifically whether the normative camps established

in 2002 created a path to which the 2011 bioethical decision-making anchored itself. The relevant evidence is therefore not coalition formation as such, but the continuity of coalitions over time as an indicator of normative self-binding.

4. State of Research

4.1 Germany as a Bioethical Special Case

The German debate on biopolitics is markedly more restrictive than in comparable Western European states. Several explanatory factors have been advanced in the literature. First, the legacy of National Socialism functions as a persistent historical warning in German political culture concerning the treatment of human life and the risks of state-sponsored eugenic intervention (Fink, 2007). This memory does not merely inform public sentiment but has been institutionalised in key aspects of German constitutional law. Second, the Basic Law (Grundgesetz) of 1949, itself a direct response to the Nazi experience, places exceptional emphasis on human dignity (Menschenwürde) as an inviolable foundational principle; an emphasis that has structured the legal and political framing of bioethical questions ever since (Banchoff, 2005; Fink, 2007).

These factors are not merely historically prior but have been actively reproduced in subsequent legislative and judicial decisions. The Embryo Protection Act of 1990 (Embryonenschutzgesetz) criminalised embryo research and selection, setting an early restrictive baseline. The Stem Cell Act of 2002, though permitting the import of embryonic stem cell lines under strict conditions, reaffirmed the basic framework of that 1990 settlement. Engeli and Rothmayr Allison (2013) show that, across a comparative sample of Western European states, Germany's regulatory trajectory is distinctively resistant to liberalisation; a finding that motivates our question of whether this resistance was also operative in 2011.

4.2 Moral-Policy Coalitions in the German Party System

A second body of literature concerns the specific structure of political alignments in German bioethics debates. Nielsen, Jelsøe and Öhman (2002) identify two distinct societal groupings that evaluate biotechnological developments critically but from different normative starting points. The first, which they term the 'blue' group, is motivated by religious-conservative values and emphasises the protection of human life from the moment of conception. The second, the 'green' group, is technologically sceptical from an ecological and anti-commercialisation standpoint, warning against the risks of uncontrolled scientific progress and the commodification of biological material. These societal orientations, Nielsen et al. argue, shape the broader moral landscape within which political decisions are made.

At the parliamentary level, Arzheimer (2015) and Engler and Dümig (2017) demonstrate that, when party discipline is suspended in Bundestag votes on morality policy, two stable cross-party coalitions form. The restrictive coalition, what Arzheimer (2015) calls the 'strange bedfellows' coalition, typically combines the majority of CDU/CSU members with the Greens, united by shared normative frames around human dignity and the risk of a 'slippery slope' (Dambruch). The permissive coalition, drawing primarily from the FDP and SPD, tends to frame issues in terms of research freedom, medical progress, and individual self-determination. The Left Party (Die Linke) is traditionally heterogeneous in bioethics questions, and since it did not exist in its current form in 2002, I largely bracket it from the comparative analysis.

Crucially for our purposes, Arzheimer (2015) and Engler and Dümig (2017) find that these coalition patterns are remarkably stable across different morality policy issues and across time. This stability is not merely the result of consistent individual preferences but reflects, I argue, a mechanism of normative self-binding that connects earlier decisions to later ones: having publicly committed to a normative position in 2002, actors face heightened costs of later

departure. Prior alignment thus functions as a form of pre-commitment that path dependence theory would predict.

5. Method

5.1 Process Tracing

The methodological approach is a qualitative, deductive, theory-testing process tracing analysis (Starke, 2023). Process tracing is suited to our purposes because it allows us to examine the step-by-step development of normative argumentative logics and political coalitions over time, moving from an independent variable to a dependent variable through an observable causal chain. Unlike correlational methods, process tracing can identify the mechanisms through which path dependence operates rather than merely inferring its presence from outcomes.

In our design, the independent variable is the structure and argumentation of the Stem Cell Act debate in 2002; specifically, the normative frames employed and the coalition patterns observable in that debate. The dependent variable is the configuration of the PID debate in 2011. The causal chain I seek to trace runs from the normative settlement of 2002, through mechanisms of self-binding, legitimacy reproduction, and coalition persistence, to the observed structure of the 2011 debate.

5.2 Data and Sources

Our primary sources are the Bundestag plenary protocols (Plenarprotokolle) of the two key debates: the 214th session of the 14th Bundestag on 30 January 2002 (Deutscher Bundestag, 2002a) and the 105th session of the 17th Bundestag on 14 April 2011, supplemented by the final roll-call vote of 7 July 2011 (Deutscher Bundestag, 2011a; 2011b). From these protocols, I extract causal-process observations (CPOs); specific, theoretically motivated observations that provide either evidence for or against the hypothesised causal mechanisms. CPOs consist of (a) explicit backward references to earlier debates or legislative acts and (b) instances of frame reproduction, that is, the deployment of normatively identical argumentative patterns.

Additional legislative reference points, the Embryo Protection Act 1990, the Stem Cell Act amendment debate of 2008, and a relevant Federal Constitutional Court (BVerfG) ruling of 2010, are not systematically analysed but are incorporated as contextual reference points where they are explicitly invoked in the primary debates. This allows us to capture the full normative heritage visible in the 2011 debate without overextending the scope of the analysis.

5.3 Operationalisation

For H1, I search the protocols for two types of evidence. First, explicit backward references; instances where a speaker in the 2011 debate directly cites the 2002 debate, the 1990 Embryo Protection Act, or earlier normative settlements as binding precedents. Second, implicit normative frame reproduction; cases where the same argumentative patterns appear in both debates without explicit citation, indicating the collective stabilisation of a shared normative vocabulary.

For H2, I examine two further dimensions. First, continuity of individual actor positions, I identify MPs who participated in both debates and assess whether their normative positioning remained consistent across 2002 and 2011. Second, continuity of cross-party coalitions, I assess whether the same overarching camps (restrictive vs. permissive) are observable in both debates, drawing on the final roll-call vote of July 2011 as quantitative supporting evidence.

Together, these four observational dimensions constitute our test of path dependence: I aim to show not simply that actors held stable moral preferences but that prior decisions created normative structures that constrained repositioning and shaped the range of legitimate arguments available in 2011.

6. Empirical Analysis

6.1 H1: Argumentative Continuity

6.1.1 Explicit Backward References (Direct Path Coupling)

The 2011 PID debate shows a striking density of explicit references to earlier legislative settlements. These references are not merely rhetorical invocations of history; they function as normative anchors that constrain the argumentative space of the debate. I identify three distinct categories of such direct path coupling.

First, multiple speakers in 2011 invoke the normative principles established in 1990 and 2002 as binding constraints on the current debate. The SPD member Ulla Schmidt articulates this most directly in what constitutes a canonical CPO for H1:

"Ein Abgehen von dem, was in den letzten 20 Jahren für uns gegolten hat, wäre ein Paradigmenwechsel in unserem Wertekanon." [A departure from what has applied to us over the last 20 years would be a paradigm shift in our value system.] (Schmidt, SPD, Bundestag, 2011)

This statement is significant not merely as an expression of personal preference but as an explicit acknowledgement that existing norms generate a presumption against change; precisely the mechanism of path dependence as described by Beyer (2023). Schmidt is not arguing that change is impossible, but that it carries an exceptional normative burden of justification.

Second, several MPs in 2011 draw explicit connections between their current positions and their own earlier contributions to the 2002 debate. This personalised form of backward reference is a particularly strong indicator of the normative self-binding mechanism, as it suggests that prior public commitments constrain later repositioning. Where individual voting records and plenary statements from both debates are available, they show a high degree of consistency.

Third, the claim that new regulations can only be legitimate if they are compatible with prior decisions is made explicitly by members of the permissive camp as well. The FDP's Sabine Leutheusser-Schnarrenberger exemplifies this:

"Das Embryonenschutzgesetz 1991 und das Stammzellengesetz 2002 folgen verfassungskonformen Linien. Genau auf diesen Linien liegt auch unser Entwurf." [The Embryo Protection Act 1991 and the Stem Cell Act 2002 follow constitutionally sound lines. Our proposal is precisely in line with those lines.] (Leutheusser-Schnarrenberger, FDP, Bundestag, 2011)

This is a revealing CPO. Even the proponent of a more permissive PID regulation feels compelled to justify her proposal as a continuation of, rather than a departure from, prior legislative lines. This is precisely what path dependence theory would predict: the accumulated legitimacy of prior settlements functions as a gatekeeping criterion for new proposals, regardless of whether the speaker belongs to the restrictive or permissive camp. The path thus constrains not only those who wish to preserve it, but also those who wish to modify it. They must do so in the path's own terms.

6.1.2 Implicit Normative Frame Reproduction

Beyond explicit references, the 2002 and 2011 debates exhibit near-identical normative argumentative structures. These implicit frame reproductions are significant for path dependence because they indicate that the normative vocabulary is not simply held by individual actors but has been collectively stabilised. It constitutes a shared argumentative 'grammar' that participants invoke independently. The following table summarises the four core frames identified in both debates:

Normative Frame	Restrictive Camp (CDU/CSU–Greens)	Permissive Camp (FDP–SPD)
Human Dignity (Menschenwürde)	Embryo as bearer of human dignity from fertilisation; any research use violates an absolute right	Dignity compatible with proportionate regulation; not equivalent to absolute ban on all use
Slippery Slope (Dambruch)	Any exception will inevitably expand; restriction must be categorical to prevent gradual erosion	Slippery slope is empirically unproven; targeted regulation can establish robust boundaries
Research Freedom (Forschungsfreiheit)	Research freedom is not absolute; limits justified by protection of life	Constitutional protection of science; international competitive pressure justifies permissive framework
Historical Responsibility (NS-Vergangenheit)	Nazi eugenics as explicit warning; Germany has special obligation of restrictiveness	Historical responsibility argues for careful regulation, not absolute prohibition; medical progress also a value

Table 1: Normative Frames in the 2002 and 2011 Bundestag Debates on Bioethics

The stability of these frames across two debates separated by nine years, involving partly different actors and addressing a different (though related) legislative question, constitutes strong evidence for H1. Crucially, the frames do not merely recur in both debates. They recur in the same configuration, with the same internal divisions and the same distribution across the same sides of the debate. The normative frame structure of 2002 appears to have been incorporated as a taken-for-granted 'background grammar' of German bioethics discourse.

This is consistent with the path dependence mechanism of increasing returns: the more frequently a normative frame is deployed and built upon, the more costly it becomes to introduce an alternative vocabulary, and the more natural the existing one appears. By 2011, the frames of Menschenwürde, Dambruch, Forschungsfreiheit and NS-Vergangenheit had been stabilised over more than two decades of legislative and judicial discourse, from the 1990 Embryo Protection Act through the 2002 Stem Cell Act and the 2008 amendment debate. The PID debate of 2011 inherited this stabilised vocabulary and reproduced it with only marginal modifications.

6.2 H2: Coalition Continuity

6.2.1 Continuity of Individual Actor Positions

The second hypothesis requires evidence of structural continuity, not merely that similar arguments were made, but that they were made by actors in the same cross-party alignments. I examine this at two levels: the continuity of individual actor positions, and the continuity of aggregate coalition patterns.

With respect to individual continuity, I identify four MPs who were active in both debates and whose positions can be traced across them. The pattern is summarised below:

Actor (Party)	Position 2002	Position 2011	Significance
Ulla Schmidt (SPD)	Restrictive	Restrictive (leading voice)	Non-dominant position within SPD in both debates; early commitment raises cost of later departure
Peter Hintze (CDU)	Liberal (party minority)	Liberal (co-initiator)	Part of internal CDU minority in both debates; co-authored the permissive PID proposal in 2011
Ulrike Flach (FDP)	Liberal	Liberal (most permissive proponent)	FDP lead voice in both debates; consistent permissive framing across issues
Patrick Meinhardt (FDP)	Liberal	Liberal	Consistent alignment with FDP liberal frame across both debates

Table 2: Continuity of Individual Actor Positions across 2002 and 2011 Debates

The cases of Ulla Schmidt and Peter Hintze are particularly theoretically instructive. Both occupied non-dominant positions within their respective parties in 2002, Schmidt as a restrictive voice in a broadly permissive SPD context, Hintze as a liberal voice within a broadly restrictive CDU. As Arzheimer (2015) and Engler and Dümig (2017) note, such early positioning in intra-party minority camps involves a form of advance commitment that is especially costly to reverse. Having publicly dissented from one's party's majority position in 2002, the normative costs of reverting to the party line in 2011 are particularly high, not only for reputational reasons, but because the original dissent was publicly justified in terms of principled normative arguments that cannot easily be discarded.

This is the mechanism of normative self-binding at the individual level: prior public commitments, especially counter-majoritarian ones, foreclose later repositioning not through institutional constraint but through argumentative consistency norms. The fact that both Schmidt and Hintze maintained their positions across nine years and a change of legislative context provides strong micro-level evidence for the path dependence mechanism.

6.2.2 Continuity of Cross-Party Coalitions

At the aggregate level, the cross-party coalition patterns documented by Arzheimer (2015) and Engler and Dümig (2017) for the 2011 PID vote replicate the structure of the 2002 debate in broad terms. The restrictive coalition continued to be anchored in the majority of CDU/CSU members and the Greens, united by the same normative frames of Menschenwürde and Dambruch. The permissive coalition continued to draw primarily from the FDP and a minority of SPD members. The 'strange bedfellows' quality of the restrictive coalition, CDU/CSU and Greens sharing a platform despite their otherwise divergent political profiles, was, if anything, more pronounced in 2011 than in 2002, as it required renewed negotiation and justification within each party.

The final roll-call vote of 7 July 2011 provides quantitative corroboration of this pattern. The three motions put to the vote, two restrictive proposals and one more permissive proposal, divided the Bundestag along lines closely resembling the 2002 alignment, with the permissive proposal (which ultimately passed) drawing a cross-party majority from FDP, SPD liberals, and a minority of CDU/CSU members, while the more restrictive proposals were supported predominantly by CDU/CSU conservatives and Greens (Deutscher Bundestag, 2011b).

It is important to note that the outcome of the 2011 vote, the passage of a regulated, and thus partially permissive, PID regime, does not contradict the path dependence argument. Path dependence does not predict that outcomes will be identical across time, but that the range of admissible alternatives will be constrained by prior decisions. The regulated PID of 2011 was the most permissive option politically available; and even that option was framed, as noted above (see Section 6.1.1), as a continuation rather than a departure from the normative lines established in 1990 and 2002. The path was not broken; it was slightly extended.

7. Discussion

The analysis of the 2002 and 2011 Bundestag debates provides substantial evidence for both hypotheses. The patterns identified are consistent with a path dependence interpretation in several respects.

For H1, the coexistence of explicit backward references and implicit normative frame reproduction in the 2011 debate suggests that the 2002 Stem Cell Act did more than establish a legal rule. It crystallised a normative vocabulary that subsequent bioethical debates were obliged to engage with, either by reaffirming or by carefully justifying departures from it. The density of explicit citations to prior legislation in 2011, including references not only to 2002 but also to the 1990 Embryo Protection Act, reflects the cumulative nature of the normative path: each new settlement adds a layer of legitimacy to the existing framework and raises the threshold for reform. This is consistent with the mechanism of 'increasing returns' as applied to normative rather than economic goods.

For H2, the persistence of the same cross-party coalition structure across two debates separated by nine years, and involving partly different legislative questions, points to a structural path that transcends individual preferences. The stability of coalition patterns is particularly significant in the German context because, in morality policy votes with suspended party discipline, actors are in principle free to position themselves entirely according to personal conviction. The fact that they do not, that the observed positions cluster into predictable groupings matching the 2002 alignment, suggests that 'free' conscience votes are not entirely free in practice. Prior normative commitments, made publicly and tied to principled arguments, constrain later repositioning through a logic of argumentative consistency that is

analogous to, if distinct from, the economic switching costs typically invoked in path dependence analysis.

This finding has implications for the broader comparative question raised by Engeli and Rothmayr Allison (2013). Their cross-national analysis identifies Germany as a restrictive outlier, explaining this outlier status primarily through structural factors, institutional veto points, the constitutional salience of human dignity, and the strength of religious-conservative coalition parties. Our analysis suggests an additional, dynamic dimension: the restrictive path is actively reproduced in each subsequent legislative episode through the normative self-binding of actors and coalitions. The restrictiveness of German bioethics regulation is not simply a structural given but is continuously re-enacted through argumentative and coalition practices.

8. Conclusion

This paper set out to test whether the configuration of the German Preimplantation Genetic Diagnosis Act of 2011 can be understood as a path-dependent continuation of prior bioethics legislation, in particular the Stem Cell Act of 2002. Drawing on a deductive, theory-testing process-tracing analysis of Bundestag plenary protocols, I found substantial evidence for both of our hypotheses.

In relation to H1, both explicit backward references and implicit normative frame reproduction in the 2011 debate confirm that the argumentative patterns established in 2002, centred on the frames of human dignity, the slippery slope, research freedom, and historical responsibility, were reproduced with high fidelity in 2011. The 2002 normative settlement functioned not merely as a legal precedent but as a legitimating grammar that new proposals were required to speak. Even the proponents of a more permissive PID regulation felt compelled to justify their position as a continuation of, rather than a departure from, the established normative lines.

In relation to H2, the same cross-party moral-policy coalitions identified in the literature for morality policy in Germany, a restrictive CDU/CSU–Greens camp and a permissive FDP–SPD camp, re-emerged in the 2011 debate with striking continuity. The analysis of individual actors who participated in both debates reveals a pattern of normative self-binding consistent with path dependence theory: early public commitments, especially non-dominant ones, constrained later repositioning and contributed to the structural stability of the coalition pattern.

Taken together, these findings confirm and extend the core results of Engeli and Rothmayr Allison (2013). Germany's regulatory restrictiveness is not only a structural product of institutional veto points and constitutional salience, it is actively reproduced in each legislative episode through normative self-binding and coalition persistence. The most recent bioethics legislation, the PID Act of 2011, is a case in point: even a regulated and partially permissive outcome was framed, negotiated, and justified within the normative path established over the preceding two decades.

Several limitations must be acknowledged. First and most importantly, a qualitative process-tracing analysis of this kind cannot demonstrate strict causality; it can identify evidence consistent with a causal claim and trace the mechanisms through which path dependence would operate, but it cannot rule out alternative explanations or demonstrate that the path was the decisive factor in the 2011 outcome. Second, our analysis is necessarily selective: it focuses on the 2002 and 2011 debates as primary sources and incorporates earlier reference points only as they appear in those debates. A more comprehensive analysis might include the 1990, 2008 and other relevant legislative episodes as full analytical targets. Third, the normative frames I identify, while empirically grounded in the protocols, involve an interpretive dimension, and alternative categorisations are conceivable.

Future research might extend this analysis in two directions. Longitudinally, tracing the full sequence from 1990 through 2002, 2008 and 2011 with equal analytical depth would allow for

a more precise assessment of when and how the normative path was established. Comparatively, applying the same process-tracing design to a non-special-case country, one where path breaking did occur, would allow for a stronger causal inference through structured comparison. Both extensions would contribute to a more robust empirical foundation for the theoretical claim that, in German bioethics policy, the path, once set, is very hard to leave.

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